

Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance working in Private Banks ...

Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance working in Private Banks in Hyderabad City

Bakhtawar Khuwaja

MPhil Scholar at Institute of Business Administration, University of Sindh, Jamshoro,
Sindh, Pakistan.

Email: bakhtawarferozalikhawaja@gmail.com

Dr. Abdul Sattar Shah

Professor and Director at Institute of Business Administration, University of Sindh,
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan

Dr. Samiuddin Shaikh

Assistant Professor at Institute of Business Administration, University of Sindh,
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

A quantitative research is conducted to determine how motivation affects employee performance and how to it can be practiced, as well as the relationship between motivation and promotion and reward programs in Pakistani private banks. Questionnaires were administered to three levels of staff including high-level, middle-level and frontline managers. A total of 280 closed questionnaires were published among participants to examine motivation and employee performance, and Smart PLS SEM was used to examine the relationship between influences and variables. The results of structural equation modeling show that there is a positive and significant relationship between motivation and employee performance. The results of the current study suggest that Pakistan's private banking industry should pay attention to rewards and promotions. Employees perform better, but receive less rewards. Prizes and rewards are not based on the number of tasks or workloads. In addition, current research and analysis have increased the importance of motivation and other human resource practices for employee performance in Pakistan's private banking sector.

Keywords: Motivation, employee performance, Private sector banks, Pakistan.

Introduction

Motivation plays a vital role in up the productivity of the worker and therefore the organization or any establishment. Additionally, prospering leadership in a corporation is one that considers people's wants because the basis for developing a strategic business arrange. Therefore, worker information needs human resources to implement giant reward

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schemes as some way to inspire them. Therefore, motivation is vital for prospering businesses as a result of it refers to underlying behaviors that are characterized by need and need for private enjoyment, interest, or job satisfaction to stimulate intrinsic motivation. (Guay et al, 2010).

In fact, Kreitner (1998) and Linder (1998) outline motivation as a psychological method that gives behavioral and directional goals. this means an inclination to figure by choice to satisfy specific desires.

As a result, he terminated that motivation could be a basic theme for up work productivity and worker performance. Additionally, several researchers, like Greeno (2012), Guay et al (2010), divide it into 2 sorts of incentives; first, the essential reasons that represent the economic advantages to the employees from their exceptional work. Second, ethical motives are outlined as incentives designed to satisfy the emotional, psychological, and humanitarian desires of staff, such as; grateful and grateful for the employees' efforts to enhance the spirituality of their geographic point. Therefore, these 2 sorts of incentives are expected to fill the analysis gap between worker ability and disposition. As a result, organizations should encourage their staff to enhance their performance and performance.

Originally, Maslow (1943) argued that everybody should be happy with the pyramid from the start by inform to the highest of the pyramid and therefore the person should meet all must get to subsequent. Maslow more argued that unmet desires produce tension and imbalance, and to realize balance, each would like should be protected to encourage unmet desires. At identical time, Gerhard Herzberg (1959) outlined the motivation constant as action, assessment, dignity and promotion. This issue drives individuals to boost up their efforts and do their best to assist win the organization's goals.

Organizations round the world evolve from national to international and international. As firms expand, firms face three-dimensional challenges, thus organizations should be stronger altogether aspects to face environmental challenges, which suggests that non-human individuals or organizations should be economical and productive in their expenses. Motivation plays an important role during this regard, because it strengthens the organization by increasing the morale of its staff. it's been found that actuated employees perform their tasks additional effectively than people who don't seem to be actuated. The importance of worker motivation can't be unnoticed or underestimated to enhance the performance of Pakistani individuals and money establishments. Motivation affects worker performance if motivation is unheeded organizations will lose valuable staff.

The background to the document was a need to enhance the reward and motivation system for Palestinian industrial banks. additionally, a culture of worker loyalty and job satisfaction still as structure performance is bolstered through a motivation issue. As a result, the aim of this study is to realize the subsequent objectives; 1st, recognize the motivation and performance of Pakistani banking staff. Second, the connection explores the relationship between the Pakistani Bank's motivation dimension and worker performance. Third, the effects of moral, material, and social motivation on the performance of Pakistani bank workers are explored.

Empirical Studies and Hypothesis Development

Motivation is a common word derived from the shorter word "motivation", which means

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several things, such as one's wants, needs, wants, and desires. Its origin is the Latin word "movere", which means to move (Ramlall 2004 cited by Kretiner 1998). It is also the name of the process that motivates people to take action to achieve a goal or purpose. "Motivation is the result of the interaction of conscious and unconscious factors, such as the intensity of desires or needs, the motivating or rewarding value of goals, and the expectations of individuals and their peers" (Ganta 2014).

A critical study of the literature of interest found that several motivational theories have been developed, which are particularly suitable for work environments. This concept was developed by Abraham Maslow. Based on the idea of using five global desires to remind employees, this set of wishes indicates that one is motivated to meet the best conditions when needed (Maslow, 1970). This need in literature taught us that it puts them together. The low desire he asserted will succeed until at least it can be satisfied. From this point of view, it is understandable that if you want to generate better demand as a steady growth-led way, then any ordinary man or woman will change his interest to meet the needs of subsequent degrees. Clayton Alderfer introduced the concept of ERG in 1972 as a brief reaction to Maslow's lack of empirical evidence on the level of causes in 1970. His purpose is to make it develop in the direction of empirical research. However, Alderfer's conceptual model of desire is based entirely on Maslow's ideas. A careful examination of the subject led to the clear conclusion that Alderfer was simply looking for an alternative technique over the principle of rejection. ERG definition; lifestyle, courtship and growth. Herzberg (1959) said that reducing dissatisfaction no longer encourages employees to do a great process, but the process that is easiest to stay in. The overall performance of employees really depends on how motivated they are, which encourages them to come back regularly, work hard to draw, bend and be willing to perform their desired duties. The performance and goodness of bank products depend on the strength and motivation of bank human resources. As a result, bankers' motivations are likely to affect the delivery and performance of banking services in terms of customer service and overall task performance.

Employee motivation and the day-to-day tools and physical facilities employees use can affect business. Poor working conditions and a lack of one or more of the elements required for a good job can lead to low employee motivation, reducing work quality and productivity. "Motivation is what drives employees to put in the effort and keep it going until they achieve the goals set by the employer" (Martin 2015). Often, motivated employees work hard to achieve their goals. Employee motivation has more aspects than extrinsic rewards or work environment. "Motivation is the result of the interaction of conscious and unconscious factors, such as the intensity of desires or needs, the motivating or rewarding value of goals, and the expectations of individuals and their peers." (Ganta 2014). When it comes to motivating team members, managers must remember to cover all aspects. "Motivation is the internal urge to satisfy unmet needs and achieve specific goals." (Dobre 2013). "A person's motivation encompasses all the reasons why he decides to act in a certain way" (Viorel et al., 2019). It is also a process initiated by a physical or psychological need that drives performance in goal setting.

Consistent with Kotelnikov (2008), the number of people who are encouraged to paint depends on the productivity of these people in their activities. His approach is similar, claiming that motivation can be expected to have a high-quality impact on good performance.

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There is no doubt that employees characterized by excessive motivation will show better painting and life satisfaction. The employees themselves have a high degree of motivation is cherished, and the reduction of the motivation stage may have a negative impact on the personnel. In this case, the motivation will lead the personnel's initiative and creativity to a better stage, and in this case It's difficult to monitor, so motivation is critical to ensuring excessively good overall performance.

After the review of literature, following hypotheses have been proposed

H1. Rewards are positively related with employee motivation

H2. Promotion is positively related with employee motivation

H3. Employee Motivation is positively related with employee performance

Conceptual Framework

Figure 01. Conceptual framework of research

Methods and Material Measure

The source of research data is Primary, which involves collecting research data directly from respondents. In other words, primary sources are direct sources of data related to a topic or issue. Here, data will be collected directly from employees in the banking industry.

The Population of Study

The subjects of the study were the general public who enjoy working in taxi services. The research subjects consisted of employees in the banking sector.

Sampling Strategy

In primary research, sampling is an important component that determines the number of respondents who participate in the study. Because of time, geographic, and financial constraints, a subset of the population must be selected for the study. The sampling process can be probability and non-probability. In this case, the technique of convenience sampling is used, which is a form of non-probability sampling and takes into account the accessibility

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and proximity of respondents.

Sample Size

The most acceptable way to define the sample is 10:1 (10 samples per unit. According to the proposed empirical rule, in the case of quantitative and multiple regression analysis, it is enough to meet the sample size criterion (number of items). * 10). In our example, the Total Number item is $10 \times 28 = 280$, and the response rate is 88%.

Structural Equation Modeling

According to TabaChnik and fidell (2006) (SEM), structural equation models involve the collection of statistical techniques, which helps to combine data with basic theory. Structural equation models are also called modeling, causal analysis, and simultaneous equation modeling, Covariance analysis structure, path analysis or confirmatory factor analysis. Bagozzi and fornell (1982) describe the analysis techniques of structural technology modeling, such as covariance-based modeling (AMOS, LISREL), component-based modeling and variance-based modeling (such as PLS), all of which are modern statistical analysis. SEM replaces the first generation of statistical tools, which can help researchers model complex relationships, handle multi linearity, perform confirmatory factor analysis, merge unobserved (i.e. potential) and observed variables, and finally estimate The variance of measurement errors (unreliable and random errors) is avoided (Rigdon et al., 1998; Hair et al., 2006; Barbara, 2001). Hair et al. (Hair et al., 2006) reported that structural studies on complex relationship and multivariate data modeling are increasingly using structural equation modeling tools in behavioral studies. Because of these prominent features, research Personnel need to collect multiple metrics for the proposed construct.

DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS

Respondents sampled while final data collection in private banks in Pakistan were majority of Males (90%) and only (10%) were females. Data collection of study were frequently married with the percentage of 80 and remaining 20% were single with frequency of 224 and 56. Furthermore, Participants sampled during final data collection have their ages ranging between 20 to 59 years, and majority with 30-39 and 20-29, with frequency of 126 and 70 thus on the basis of final data analysis most of the employee of private banks are young The academic background of respondents is based on bachelor degree (25%), Master degree (72.5%) and MPhil / Phd (2.5%) with frequency of 70, 203 and 7. Final data analysis described that a well skilled employment work force is employed, consequently there in the organizations, when employee are well skilled and well capable could work to achieve and even go further than set objectives at all time, meanwhile their experience ranging between less than 1 year to 40 years and nearly every employee having 1 to 10 years of experience and on second 21 to 30 of experience, therefore on the basis of final data analysis most of the employee of private banks are 1 to 10 years experienced. The frequency of occupational background during final data analysis of participants in private banking sector in Pakistan is consisting on Top level management (7.5%), Middle level management (35%) and First line management (57.5%) with percentage of 21, 98 and 161.

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Algorithm Model Findings

Table.1 consists of convergence effectiveness. Fornell & Larcker (1981) describes the degree to which two measures of convergence effectiveness are related to the same concept. Hair et al. (2010) reported that this is the degree of difference between two conceptually similar concepts, which ensures that each latent variable shares more variance with its own block. The one-dimensionality of the degree is proven. An indicator with another potential variable. (Tab.1) The correlation on the diagonal is higher than the correlation between other structures. Here, from (Tab.2), it is found that the AVE of the latent variable EM is 0.883, so its square root is 0.939, which is larger than the correlation value (0.717, 0.326) in the EM column, and also larger than the EM row. The AVE similar to EPER is 0.716 , Its square root becomes 0.846, which is larger in the column of EPER and larger in the row of EPER, which indicates that the structure is relatively separated and the operability is strong. The same observations were made for other potential variables.

**Table 1. Correlation on the diagonal of constructs
 Convergent - Divergent**

Variable	RD	EM	EPER	EPRO
Reward	0.780			
Employee Motivation	0.651	0.939		
Employee Performance	0.748	0.717	0.846	
Employee Promotion	0.720	0.326	0.669	0.881

The mean variance (AVE) internal consistency reliability or composite reliability explained in Table 2. R square and Cronbachs Alpha. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), AVE values greater than 0.5 are considered good. All variables here have strong AVE values. The highest AVE value is employee motivation (EM), the value is 0.883, and the lowest value is Reward (RD), which is 0.609. The reliability of the composite material should be 0.7 or higher. For interpretive studies, 0.6 or higher is acceptable. (Bagozzi and Yi, 1988). The internal consistency reliability is very acceptable here. All variables have strong composite reliability, and their values are 0.886 (EM), 0.938 (EM), and 0.882 (EPER). And 0.874 (EPRO). It shows that the internal consistency index is better loaded into its own structure than other structures.

R-squared is the coefficient of determination. It is a measure of how much the external (independent) observed variables explain the difference in results (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007; Hair et al., 2006). It is similar to the squared multiple correlation coefficient (SMC) based on covariance. (EPRO) has a weaker R Square, but in the literature (Rosenthal and Rubin, 1982) opposes the use of R Square, although other variables have good R Square values, as described in Table 2. Measuring the one-dimensionality (cross-correlation) of indicators using a latent construct. (Cronbach, 1951). The Cronbach alpha coefficient of this study is close to 0.7 or higher, which indicates that the scale used in this study to measure different observed variables for each construct has appropriate internal consistency (Forman & Nyatanga, 2001; Sekaran, 2000; Hair, Bush, and Austria Tino (2000).

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**Table 2. Overview of correlation among constructs
 Overview**

Variable	AVE	Composite Reliability	R Square	Cronbachs Alpha
Reward	0.609	0.886	0.518	0.842
Employee Motivation	0.883	0.938	0	0.868
Employee Performance	0.716	0.882	0.744	0.800
Employee Promotion	0.776	0.874	0.106	0.713

Bootstrapping Model Findings

In the structural model of the second path analysis phase, we resampled 500 times (the bootstrap method) to obtain the t-statistic and the standard deviation estimates of the load and path coefficients (Hair et al., 2010). Table 3. lists the path coefficient effects, total effects, β and T statistics for the entire project in a dimensional model where almost all metrics have a high load.

**Table 3. Path Coefficient
 Path Coefficient**

Hypotheses	Beta	Standard Error	T Statistics
RD -> EM	0.240	0.063	3.802
EM -> EPER	0.446	0.042	10.444
EPRO -> EM	0.720	0.023	31.735

If the T statistic is greater than 1.96, the path coefficient will be important. There are studies in market research and 1.65 in interpretation research (Hair et al., 2010). According to Table 3. of the study, there is a significant relationship between all variables. Here, the relationship between employee promotion (PRO) and employee motivation (EM) is very important, with a value of 31.735, and the relationship between second employee motivation (EM) and employee performance (PER) is very important, with a value of 10.444. The worst correlation is the correlation between RD and EM, which is also 3.803 higher than the value required for importance. Therefore, there is a very significant correlation between all variables.

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that different variables of employee motivation affect the performance of Pakistani private banks and employee career development practices. The findings of the study on the private banking industry in Pakistan show that employee motivation (EM) is a major factor affecting other employee-related variables, such as employee promotion (EPRO) and employee performance (EPER), and this finding confirms (Cleveland Et al., 1989; Campbel et al., 1970; Levine, 1986; Rendero, 1980. This shows that employee enthusiasm is closely related to employee promotion and employee performance, and encourages employees to work hard to help promote employees, and promotion helps employees improve performance .

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Employee promotion (EPRO) also affects employee performance, suggesting that employee promotion can increase employee satisfaction with their work and improve employee performance. This finding validates the findings of Shelton (2001) and Umer (2011), when organizations were employees Provides opportunities for growth and development. Developments such as different courses and educational sponsorships, and then because of lack of professional development, employees are more satisfied with their work and employees leave the organization. The findings of this study are also consistent with the findings of (Edirisooriya, 2014), which points to the close relationship between bonuses, benefits and promotions and employee performance. Based on the results of Pratheepkanth (2011), he also concluded that external rewards have a positive effect on employee performance. Reward (RD) also has a significant impact on employee performance (EPER). According to the findings of this study, those employees who get a return from work and perform better. Satisfied employees perform better than unsatisfied employees in the organization. The findings of this study are related to the findings of Pushpakumari (2008) that rewards have a significant impact on the performance of employees in private sector organizations. Satisfied employees may focus on working on time and worry more about a given goal.

This research is an explanatory study based on complex investigative strategies. e. PLS Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and such studies. In the context of performance evaluation, this study contributed to the private banking sector in Pakistan through a structural equation model and linked it to employee promotions at specific private banks in Pakistan. Considering the limitations of the above studies, some future research directions are given below:

- Research should focus on redefining and exploring metrics, especially those used to measure employee motivation and employee career growth activities and job performance in the context of Pakistan's private banking industry. More attention should be paid to larger private and public The department organizes the size and population of managers and non-managers of government and private banks. The scale that is determined to be valid here should be tested and checked again to indicate whether the results of this study are valid The ultimate goal of future research should be to develop measurement models in the context of structural model representation, the overall impact of performance incentive performance practices on employee performance, and other elements of research in Pakistan.
- Most research on this topic ignores developing countries in general, and Pakistan in particular, and therefore belongs to the developed countries of the world and Western countries or fast developing countries in the Middle East or Asia. Unexpectedly, from a perspective, employee promotion activities, responsibilities promotion and salary promotion are all based on the experience of employees and the personal relationship between the head of the private sector bank and their subordinates, and because the responsibilities are above average, employees are not satisfied In other words, employees have the view that compensation is usually not dependent on performance. Therefore, future research should focus on this and analyze these issues in the context of Pakistan's private banking industry.
- Pakistan's private banking sector will quickly redefine motivations, rewards and recognition activities to enhance and improve employee performance in private banks, and rewards and other rewards should be based on the country's economic situation, namely

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inflation. This research helps the private banking sector make the right use of human resource management practices so they can get more from their employees. The findings of this study are closely related to and verified by the findings of (Bowra et al., 2012). After considering these four most important HR practices, future research can be completed by considering other HR practices (such as employee organization commitment, training, and developing practice appeal practices).

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